

Developing an Architecture Method Library

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Abstract

Today, there are millions of professionals worldwide acting as a designer, architect or engineer in the design, realization, and implementation of information systems. At this moment there is no well established and clearly identified body of knowledge that defines their profession in a "standard" way.

In this article, we present the idea of developing an architecture method library. Such a library could play a pivotal role to further professionalize the field. The library contains project experiences, reference architectures, literature, proven methods, tools, etc.

Access mechanisms allow the professional to use this body of knowledge. By giving it an open nature, it can be filled by professionals from different fields. Feedback mechanisms are possible to improve the contents of the library, for example by giving feedback on the method components in the library.

1. Introduction

The design, realization, and implementation of information systems provides employment to millions of professionals worldwide. When attempting to clearly identify their profession, one discovers that there does not exist a well established and clearly identified body of knowledge.

The Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK) project [SWE01] started from a similar observation for the field of software engineering. The following motivation of the SWEBOK project is provided:

In other engineering disciplines, the accreditation of university curricula and the licensing and certification of practicing professionals are taken very seriously. These activities are seen as critical to the constant upgrading of professionals and, hence, the improvement of the level of professional practice. Recognizing a core body of knowledge is pivotal to the development and accreditation of university curricula and the licensing and certification of professionals.

This inspired us to develop an architecture method library, containing project experiences, reference architectures, literature, proven methods, tools, etc.

Using various kinds of access mechanisms the professional is able to use this library. By giving it an open nature, it can be filled by professionals from different fields and with different backgrounds. Feedback mechanisms can be used to improve the contents of the library by e.g. giving feedback on the method components present based on the actual use of the library.

This article describes the design of such an architecture method library, what it contains, the way it is filled and how it can be used. Some future directions are given. In section 7 an extended example is given to illustrate the results from the other sections.

2. Restrictions on the scope of the library

Given the unclear boundaries of the information systems engineering field (what is part of this domain and what is not?), we use the following definition of information system:

An *information system* is a sub-system of an organizational system, comprising the communication- and information-oriented aspects of the organization system [FHL⁺98].

In this article, the term information systems engineering is used to refer to all activities involved in the design,

realization and implementation of information systems (including non-IT or non-automated aspects). This essentially ranges from the high level design of a portfolio of information systems (an information architecture) to the design and realization of a specific information system.

We use an organic approach to the development of the architecture method library. This essentially means that no strong restrictions are set on the scope of the library beforehand. It will emerge from the content as more is added. This fits with the fact that most of the knowledge available on information systems engineering is in case-based form, tied to experiences learned from specific cases from industrial practice.

For this moment, the demarcation lies in the group of professionals responsible for providing the content: those people who consider themselves to be architects or information systems engineers.

We realize that we cannot aim to develop a fully integrated and completely consistent architecture method library. Reasons for this are (among others) the huge amount of literature in the information systems field, the ‘vagueness’ of the field (and, subsequently, the various backgrounds of the professionals involved), and the case based nature. Therefore, we aim to compile and structure a library filled with a collection of significant, loosely coupled ‘knowledge items’ or ‘method components’, considered useful to project members of an information systems engineering project. These method components consist of focused denotations of knowledge pertaining to information systems engineering.

3. Related work

Related work can be found in e.g. [DGC⁺97] and [FHL⁺98]. In [DGC⁺97], a model curriculum is described for undergraduate degree programs in information systems and it also contains a definition of a body of knowledge for information systems engineering. The Framework for Information Systems Concepts (FRISCO) as reported in [FHL⁺98] aims to give the field of information systems a conceptual underpinning by introducing a unified framework of concepts. What both of these approaches lack is the practical side in terms of concrete work practices, techniques and tools to be used, etc.

Another field that is of relevance is the field of method engineering [BLW96, Har97]. The approach taken there tends to dissect methods to the level of distinct concepts and their relationships. For the moment, it involves too much detail to be applied to the gathering and structuring of a library of knowledge items. However, the theories provided by method engineering are useful in dissecting method knowledge into more elementary items and will also be useful for developing a consistent body of method

knowledge once a significant collection of knowledge items has been gathered into our architecture method library.

4. Contents of the library

The architecture method library should contain information about various architecture and information systems subjects, such as:

- project strategies,
- case studies (both successes and failures),
- descriptions of methods, techniques and tools,
- reference models and frameworks,
- heuristics on the use of project strategies, methods, techniques, etc.,
- knowledge to aid in planning and execution of projects,
- heuristics and guidelines with regard to design decisions, the use of reference models, architecture principles, etc.

The intended audience of the library includes managers, architects, designers, engineers, etc. In the next sections it is shown how we intend to dissect this knowledge into focused ‘knowledge items’ or ‘method components’ as we will call them below.

First, method components and a characterization of them are introduced. This is followed by situational factors and heuristics. Finally, the complete structure of the library is given.

4.1. Method components

In literature on method engineering, frameworks are found that basically provide an anatomy of a method. See for example [FGH96, WH90]. This has led us to define our framework for building an architecture method library on five “standard” questions, which can be identified with the following method components:

- *Product*. Based on the question “what has to be delivered?”
- *Activity*. Based on the question “what has to be done to obtain the deliverable?”
- *Actor*. Based on the question “who will be doing it and what capabilities do they need?”
- *Tool*. Based on the question “what tools can be used?”
- *Principle*. Based on the question “what architecture principles have to be used?”

4.2. Characterization of method components

Each method component has to be characterized so that a potential user is able to judge whether that component may be of use to him. For example, for a modeling technique, it is important to know for what types of modeling it may be used for: e.g. for modeling of business processes, for modeling of organizational structures, for communication, etc.

For this purpose, we define *properties* with *property values*. During the development of the library it will be discovered which of them are useful and which not. Examples of such properties are:

- *System scope*. What is the scope of the method component in terms of the system(s) considered? Some examples are: portfolio of systems, family of systems, specific system, and specific use-case.
- *Systemic focus*. What system is the method component focused at? Some options are: organizational system, information system, computerized information system, and infrastructural system.
- *Systemic aspect*. Zachman has identified a number of different aspects of a system [Zac87], based on the interrogatives of the English language. This leads to aspects such as: what, how, when, why, and where.
- *Level of abstraction*. What level of abstraction, with respect to the systems under consideration, is the method component focused at? Examples (derived from [ISO87]) are: conceptual level, logical level, and physical level.
- *Communication style*. What is the communication style used in describing the method component? Some examples are: reference material, study material, and teaching material.
- *Natural language used*. What is the language used to express the method component? Examples are: Dutch, English, American English, German, and French.
- *Development cycle*. Where in the development cycle can the method component be positioned? For example, activities can belong to the following aspects: delivery approach, construction approach, cognitive approach, social approach, development approach, quality control, and configuration control [FV99b].

The characterization can be seen as being orthogonal to the method components. An illustration is given in figure 1.

		method components				
		product	activity	actor	tool	principle
characterization	system scope					
	systemic focus					
	systemic aspect					
	level of abstraction					
	communication style					
	nat. language used					
	development cycle					

- delivery approach
- construction approach
- cognitive approach
- social approach
- development approach
- quality control
- configuration control

Figure 1. The method component characterization can be seen as being orthogonal to the method components. The aspects of 'activities' of the characterization 'development cycle' are shown as example.

4.3. Situational factors

For each method component in the library, there may exist various situational factors which determine its applicability. In this context, a situational factor is defined as:

A situational factor is a property of the problem situation that can be used to determine the most appropriate problem-solving strategy. This includes those properties that can have an impact on the different types of uncertain events which may occur and their adverse consequences [FV99a].

A situational factor is important since it determines how a method component can be used and how it can be adapted to a specific situation. And, vice versa, given a specific situation, the situational factor indicates which method components have been proven to work in that specific situation.

For the library, this means that it is necessary for the user to be able to select method components based on the situation at hand. Therefore, there has to be a way to specify the

Figure 2. The structure of the library.

situational factors. This is done by giving them a name and a value, e.g.

```

name = CompanyType
value = {Financial company, Public company, Industrial
        company, ...}

```

4.4. Heuristics

The situational factors are linked to the method components by using heuristics. A heuristic is a rule-of-thumb specifying which method component can be used in which situation. This is represented using an IF...THEN... rule with a logical expression about the project situation at hand in the IF part and the method component to be used in that situation in the THEN part. For example:

```

IF the complexity of the data to model is high
THEN it can be recommended to use a modeling technique
     based on natural language

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Another example based on the relation between two method components is:

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IF a participatory approach is used in the architects team
THEN it can be recommended to have a socially skillful
     team

```

4.5. Structure of the library

The complete structure of the library is given in figure 2. It is a collection of situational factors, heuristics, activities, tools, etc. which are coupled by relations. The heuristics specify which relations can be applied when. The properties define the method components and are being used in the heuristics. In section 7 (extended example), examples of method components, attributes, and the relations between them can be found.

5. Using the library

Project members can use the architecture method library to find the answers to questions such as:

- Which activities, techniques and tools are most appropriate given a specific project situation and task?
- What reference models are relevant for my project?
- What reference models are relevant in a situation where the business has selected “customer intimacy” as in [TW97] as their strategic focus?
- What are relevant architecture principles?
- Which reference models represent a front/mid/back office architecture?
- Which guidelines are useful for designing a data model?
- What methods can be used for designing an application architecture in a process intensive environment?

Just like a regular (physical) library, the architecture method library is meant to *assist* professionals. That means that the content in the library may help users in deciding, for example, which activities are appropriate in a certain project situation. The library will then present several possibilities, but only judgment of the professional will make this usable in a project context. As always, the expert is responsible for decisions made.

When the architecture method library is used, the general steps for answering questions like those above are the following:

1. Analysis of the situation at hand.
2. Selection of base method components for the question(s) at hand.
3. Selection of other useful method components. This step can be repeated as desired.
4. Use of all the method components selected helps to complete the analysis.

All this can be done by accessing the library. Adding these steps to the structure of the library as given in figure 2, the subsequent figure 3 results.

There are three different ways to access components of the library. The first method is to formulate an exact *query*. One formulates a question based on logical expressions with values for various properties. This is used as a query to the library. Examples of these kinds of queries are given at the beginning of this section.

Figure 3. An example use of the library.

Often, it is not easy to formulate an exact query like this. In such situations, browsing and selecting relevant method components may be more appropriate. This is often called: *query by navigation*.

The third method of accessing the library is the use of a more-or-less predefined *decision tree*. Using such a tree as a guideline helps to investigate the situation with which the user is confronted. The base for this are situation factors and heuristics which are used to select the applicable method components.

Of course all three access methods can be combined. After an initial selection has been made, more can be added at will. This results in a more refined analysis, as is indicated by the curved arrows in figure 3. Method components selected may (left open arrow) or may not (right open arrow) lead to additional or revised analysis. In section 7, the different access mechanisms are illustrated.

6. Filling the library

Filling the library is an iterative process. That means that adding new documents to the library is an ever continuing process.

Examples of new, not yet analyzed documents are project deliverables, project archives, textual descriptions of methods, techniques and tools, case descriptions, etc. From the perspective of the library, this material is not likely to be

very homogeneous with respect to the method components which are already present. For example, a book on some modeling method could discuss this technique in a way that is highly intertwined with a specific tool that can be used to produce the models which is already present in a method component in the library. This relation can only be added after (extensive) analysis of each source document.

After addition of these new documents, in the following step this analysis is performed. From the source document, the method components are extracted and described in a framework as described in the previous section. During this step, the relations with other method components already in the library are determined. This is often a time consuming task. The resulting material is homogeneous in nature.

In principle, anything can be added to the library. However, when quality criteria are used for “screening” new raw material, the time necessary for adding extracted method components can be reduced drastically. Criteria can be:

- Is the new source document in some way structured (the structure may lead to easier identification of method components)?
- Is the knowledge present in the new source document an addition to knowledge already present in the library (preventing double occurrences of the same method component)?
- Does the material fit in the domain of the library (preventing the addition of irrelevant material)?
- Is the knowledge expected to be interesting for more than one specific customer or situation (preventing the addition of material which is too specific to be used elsewhere)?

As can be seen, adding material to the library is a non-trivial task which has to be done by an experienced architect. Guidelines are important to prevent differences in interpretation of the raw material and to prevent different phrasings. In the next section the importance of this is illustrated. However, one should realize that such differences cannot be prevented completely.

Other, general maintenance tasks for the library can be done by a qualified “librarian”.

An additional step may be the rewriting of method components to some form of “standard terminology”. In this phase aggregation can be executed, as well as normalization of terminology and concepts used. However, this will take a substantial amount of time and the usefulness of such an exercise is not clear at this moment.

Figure 4. Two examples with method components from [SS97]. The italicized line indicates the type of method component, and the other lines the name, which in some cases can be found in the text. See the text for further explanation.

7. Extended example

In this section an extended example is discussed. We have taken [SS97] as raw material.

7.1. Filling the library

The analysis was started by checking the criteria from section 6: we have found this book to be structured, the knowledge was not in our architecture method library, the scope did fit and since it is a general purpose architecture method book, it was certainly interesting for more than one specific customer or situation.

First, we identified the various kinds of method components (cf. sections 4.1 to 4.4) and next the relations between them.

For each method component, a number of attributes was determined: most importantly a (reference) name and a short description (which can be seen as a citation or short summary). Then there are additional fields such as the reference to the book, the page numbers, etc. The library is flexible so more fields can be added as necessary.

Below, we will only show (for brevity) some of the method components identified from [SS97]. Also, in figure 4 only a few of the method components identified from this book are shown.

Situational factors

Name: organizable and manageable coherence.

Description: coupling of systems determines the coherence of the resulting information system.

Reference: [SS97].

Page: 49.

Name: reliability in exploitation.

Description: relates to the capability of a system to maintain its level of performance under stated conditions for a stated period of time.

Reference: [ISO/IEC 9126 standard].

Name: efficiency in exploitation.

Description: relates to the relationship between the level of performance of a system and the amount of resources used, under stated conditions.

Reference: [ISO/IEC 9126 standard] (reference and pages for brevity omitted from now on).

Principle

Name: infrastructural approach.

Description: infrastructural rules guide the (partly) autonomous processes. There are two layers: one with applications and one with reusable software components. The infrastructure is common for both layers.

Name: functional decomposition.

Description: functional decomposition allows applications to use common centralized data and reusable software components.

Activity

Name: information architecture design.

Description: using the foundation business model, the infrastructural components (function model and data maintenance system) and the business organization (organization model) are determined. Using the organization model and the system architecture the applications, data, and coherence between them are developed.

Property

Name: aspect of the system to model.

Description: this is the perspective of the system to model.

Products

Name: foundation business model.

Description: global, independent model of the business. Contains the purpose and a description of some sub models: job model, interaction model and object model (last model not shown in the lower part of figure 4).

Heuristics

In this example, heuristics are found in the upper part of figure 4, in the relations between the situational factors and

other method components (from the top most row to the second row) (cf. section 4.4).

Relations between method components

The relations are shown as arrows in figure 4.

The construction of other method components is similar.

7.2. Creating the network

After identifying the method components and relations, a network as shown in figure 4 can be constructed automatically. Since for this example only one book was taken and not all method components and relations have been drawn, it is only a very small network. One can imagine that the network is larger when all method components and relations from [SS97] are drawn, and that the network is even larger when method components and relations from other documents are present.

Now the importance of a unified framework comes into view: whenever the professionals filling the library do not use the same framework, the network cannot be constructed automatically.

In addition, it can be seen why adding a new document is a non-trivial task: the relation with all the existing method components must be identified. Also, the correspondence between method components from the new document and already existing ones must also be identified. See for example the method component “job model”. This relation was explicit in [SS97] so it could be identified easily. But it could have been that this document was already represented in the library. In that case the the two networks would have been linked.

7.3. Using the library

In section 5 the various access mechanisms to the architecture method library have been discussed. For answering exact queries the method components are accessed directly using some kind of query language. Query by example can be done using networks as discussed in the previous section by going from node to node using the relations and marking the interesting ones. Access using a decision tree resembles using a network which has pre-marked nodes; the professional will not “see” the non-marked nodes. Again, he or she can mark the interesting ones.

After browsing the architecture method library, the expert obtains a list of selected method components and relations between them. These can then be used in e.g. a project plan.

8. Future directions

Eventually, once the library has been filled with a reasonable number of method components, a core body of knowledge for information systems engineering may be identified. Such an explicit and accepted body of knowledge would, for example:

- Allow universities and training institutes to tune their curricula to a well defined body of knowledge accepted by both industry and academia.
- Allow for the identification of distinct roles in the information system engineering process and related forms of certification.
- Allow managers of information systems engineering projects to constitute project teams with professionals who share a common terminology and understanding of the profession.
- Allow client organizations to organize second opinion reviews among providers of information system engineering.
- Allow for re-use of experiences and materials between practitioners from different backgrounds.

Ideally, the library should make use of a common and unified conceptual framework. This will require several iterations of analysis of the library.

Once the library becomes filled with some critical mass of assets, it may become part of a “learning cycle”. The actors in an information systems engineering project who use the knowledge in the library for their project activities will be able to give feedback on the contents of the library based on their experiences in a project.

Of course, these experiences should be added to the library, resulting in an open library where professionals submit method components or refinements of existing ones to the library.

9. Conclusion

In this paper we have presented an architecture method library which eventually may evolve to some kind of information systems engineering body of knowledge. Discussed are the restrictions on the scope of the library, the contents of the library, how the library can be used and how it can be filled, and finally future directions. Also, an extended example has been provided.

This project is a collaboration between the Dutch Ordina group and the University of Nijmegen. We are currently in the process of gathering information systems engineering

knowledge within the context of the Ordina group. We appreciate contributions of other companies, research groups and universities and invite them to join our effort in gathering and structuring the architecture method library.

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